

**Republic of Zambia
Ministry of Agriculture**

**NATIONAL STRATEGY FOR CONSERVATION AND
SUSTAINABLE USE OF PLANT GENETIC RESOURCES FOR
FOOD AND AGRICULTURE**

2023 – 2027

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

BCN	Biodiversity Community Network
CAADP	Comprehensive Africa Agricultural Development Program
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CBU	Copperbelt University
CGDT	Crop Genetic Diversity Trust
CIAT	International Centre for Tropical Agriculture
CIMMYT	International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center
CTDT	Community Technology Development Trust
CSOs	Civil Society Organizations
CWRs	Crop Wild Relatives
DNPW	Department of National Parks and Wildlife
DoA	Department of Agriculture
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FISP	Farmer Input Support Programme
GART	Golden Valley Agricultural Research Trust
GIZ	Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit

GPA	Global Plan of Action
ICARDA	International Center for Agriculture Research in the Dry Areas
ICRISAT	International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics
ICT	Information Communication Technology
IITA	International Institute for Tropical Agriculture
IRRI	International Rice Research Institute
ITPGRFA	International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture
KATC	Kasisi Agriculture Training Centre
MCT	Ministry of Commerce and Trade
MLNREP	Ministry of Land, Natural Resources and Environment Protection
MoF	Ministry of Finance
MoJ	Ministry of Justice
NPFS	National Program for Food Security
NAIP	National Agricultural Investment Plan
NAIS	National Agricultural Information Services
NBA	National Biosafety Authority

NBSAP	National Biodiversity Strategic Action Plan
NDP	National Development Plans
NEPAD	New Partnership for Africa’s Development
NFNC	National Food and Nutrition Commission
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
NISIR	National Institute for Scientific and Industrial Research
NORAD	Norwegian Agency for Development Cooperation
NPGRC	National Plant Genetic Resources Centre
NPGRCom	National Plant Genetic Resources Committee
NRDC	National Resources Development College
PELUM	Participatory Ecological Land Use Management
PGRFA	Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture
PPD	Policy and Planning Department
SADC	Southern African Development Community
SCCI	Seed Control and Certification Institute
SDC	Swiss Development & Cooperation agency
SIDA	Swedish International Development Agency
SNAP	Second National Agricultural Policy

SPGRC	SADC Plant Genetic Resources Centre
SPFS	Special Program for Food Security
THPAZ	Traditional Healing Practitioners Association of Zambia
TRIPS	Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Right
UNFCC	United Nations Climate Change Convention
UNZA	University of Zambia
WTO	World Trade Organization
WWF	World Wide Fund for Nature
ZAAB	Zambia Alliance for Agroecology & Biodiversity Conservation
ZASTA	Zambia Seed Traders Association
ZARI	Zambia Agriculture Research Institute
ZEMA	Zambia Environmental Management Agency
ZNFU	Zambia National Farmers Union

DEFINITION OF TERMS

Agrobiodiversity: Includes all biodiversity components relevant for agricultural production, including food production, sustaining livelihoods and habitat conservation of agricultural ecosystems (CIP-UPWARD, 2003).

Biodiversity: The variability among living organisms from all sources including, *interalia*, terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are part; this includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems (CBD, 1992).

Ex situ collection: Collection of plant genetic resources for food and agriculture maintained outside their natural habitat.

Ex situ conservation: Conservation of biodiversity outside its natural habitat; in the case of plant genetic resources conservation can be in seed banks, in vitro collections in germplasm banks, or as live collections in the field.

Genetic material: Any material of plant, animal, microbial or other origin containing functional units of heredity (CBD, 1992).

Germplasm: The reproductive or vegetative propagating material of plants (FAO, 1993).

GPA: The Global Plan of Action on PGRFA adopted at the Fourth International Technical Conference on Plant Genetic Resources (FAO, 2010).

GRFA: “Any material of plant origin, including reproductive and vegetative propagating material, containing functional units of heredity” (ITPGRFA, 2009)

***In situ* conservation:** The conservation of ecosystems and natural habitats and the maintenance and recovery of viable populations of species in their natural surroundings and, in the case of domesticated or cultivated plant species, in the surroundings where they have developed their distinctive properties (ITPGRFA, 2009).

International Treaty on PGRFA (ITPGRFA): The only multilateral instrument regulating the conservation and sustainable use of plant genetic resources for food and agriculture.

Multilateral System of the ITPGRFA: A system that allows the exchange between Contracting Parties of genetic diversity and information associated with genetic diversity located in genebanks and ensuring the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of their use (ITPGRFA & FAO, 2013).

NISM: The National Information Sharing Mechanism on implementation of GPA-PGRFA is one tool for transparent and effective monitoring of the implementation of GPA; its objective is also to improve countries’ capacity in exchanging and analyzing PGRFA information for future planning (FAO, 2010).

Participatory plant breeding: Application of methodologies of genetic improvement, with the involvement and active participation of farmers in all the technological innovation process (FAO, 2011).

Plant genetic resources for food and agriculture (PGRFA): Any genetic material of plant origin of actual or potential value for food and agriculture (ITPGRFA, 2009).

Resilience: The capacity of an organism, ecosystem or community to recover from major disturbance events (Thompson, 2011).

Traditional knowledge: Knowledge, innovations and practices of indigenous communities embodying traditional lifestyles relevant for the conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity (CBD, 1992).

Value chain: The full range of activities which are required to bring a product or service from conception, through the different phases of production (involving a combination of physical transformation and the input of various producer services), delivery to final consumers and final disposal after use (Kaplinsky and Morris, 2001).

Variety: A plant grouping, within a single botanical taxon of the lowest known rank, defined by the reproducible expression of its distinguishing and other genetic characteristics (ITPGRFA, 2009). According to the context, it can refer to breeds and “native” or local varieties, as well as to improved, hybrids and commercial varieties.

FOREWORD

Plant genetic resources are the biological basis of increased nutrition and food security and support the livelihoods of the increasing human population. Plant genetic resources for food and agriculture (PGRFA) consist of diversity of seeds and planting material of traditional varieties and modern cultivars, crop wild relatives and other wild plant species. These resources are used as food, livestock feed, cotton fiber, clothing, shelter and energy. The conservation and sustainable use of PGRFA is necessary to ensure sustainable crop production in the face of climate change. The erosion of these resources poses a severe threat to the world's food and nutrition security in the long term.

The National Strategy for Conservation and Sustainable Use of Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture has been prepared in a participatory approach involving key national stakeholders with initial support through the TCP/SFS/3402 Project, "Support for the development of national strategies for plant genetic resources for food and agriculture" complemented by support through the fourth call Project of the Treaty's Benefit Sharing Fund, "Harnessing dryland legume and cereals genetic resource for food and nutrition security and resilient farming systems in Malawi and Zambia".

This strategy document aims to promote and ensure the rationalized conservation and management of plant genetic resources for food and agriculture in the country. It presents a succinct review of the status of plant genetic resources management in Zambia, identifies the emerging challenges and formulates a National Plan of Action for the coming 5 years with a set of key actions covering conservation and utilization, enabling legal environment, strengthening capacities for PGRFA research and development and of local communities, technical staff and decision makers in a comprehensive integrated approach.

This strategy as a tool for policy guidance in the conservation and sustainable use of PGRFA calls for aligning the activities relevant to the International Treaty of Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture with other long-term national development plans relevant to the Convention on Biological Diversity.

Green Mbozi
Permanent Secretary
MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE

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We are indebted to the sources of funding for the development of the national strategy. The National Strategy for Conservation and Management of PGRFA in Zambia has been prepared with initial support through the TCP/SFS/3402 Project, "Support for the development of national strategies for plant genetic resources for food and agriculture of 2013" complemented by support through the fourth call Treaty supported Project, "Harnessing dryland legume and cereals genetic resource for food and nutrition security and resilient farming systems in Malawi and Zambia".

The development of this strategy was made possible through the commitment of the Technical Review Team drawn from Ministry of Land and Natural Resources, Community Technology Development Trust (CTDT), Department of Forestry, Zambia Agriculture Research Institute, Department of Biological Sciences of the University of Zambia, Seed Control and Certification Institute (SCCI) and SADC Plant Genetic Resources Centre (SPGRC). I wish to specifically thank the following team members for their valuable contribution to the compilation of the strategy: Mr. Charles Nkhoma, Mr. Godfrey Mwila,

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A handwritten signature in dark purple ink, consisting of stylized cursive letters that appear to read 'I. Mukuka'.

Ivor Mukuka

Director- Zambia Agriculture Research Institute
MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

The Government of the Republic of Zambia has embarked on the diversification of the economy with the agriculture sector, among others, taking a central position as the main driver of economic development, employment creation and poverty reduction. Among the key objectives of the agricultural sector is the reduction of the country's food and nutrition insecurity situation. Currently, it is estimated that 46.7% of the population is chronically undernourished. The Government has embarked on the implementation of a number of programmes which include the Special Program for Food Security (SPFS) and the National Program for Food Security (NPFS) towards achieving this objective. These programmes are backed by national policy frameworks, plans and strategies which include the Second National Agricultural Policy (SNAP) with provisions such as crop diversification where the Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (PGRFA) anchors, National Agricultural Investment Plan (NAIP) and the National Development Plans (NDP). These frameworks are linked to the provisions of the Comprehensive Africa Agricultural Development Program (CAADP) of the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD) under the auspices of the Southern African Development Community (SADC).

Zambia has continued to implement programmes to increase food production significantly in order to feed the ever growing population and to increase the contribution of the agricultural sector to economic growth. However, challenges such as the effects of climate change have adversely impacted on the production and productivity of all crops including food crops. There is a growing realization that the optimal management of PGRFA through its effective conservation, development and deployment of crop varieties that are resilient, efficient in use of inputs and high yielding in farmers' fields has great

potential in raising the productivity and production of these crops. In order to harness this potential, it is necessary that a national strategy for PGRFA is put in place to provide a coherent framework for the implementation of interventions for the proper management and sustainable use of PGRFA.

Small-holder farmers and local communities play an essential role in the development, maintenance and use of agricultural biodiversity. Improvements in agricultural production brought about through the use of improved crop varieties have been possible because of the rich and varied genetic diversity in farmers' landraces, together with genetic material from wild and weedy species. Farmers' Rights are important in enabling farmers to maintain, develop, and utilize plant genetic diversity, and in recognizing and rewarding them for their contribution to the global genetic pool and food security. Implementing Farmers' Rights is central to the fight against poverty and eradication of hunger in the affected communities. As recognized in the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (ITPGRFA), the realization of Farmers' Rights largely rest with national governments. The National Strategy for PGRFA (2023-2027) is built upon the National Strategy of 2013-2018, whose goal was to promote the enhanced conservation and efficient and sustainable use of PGRFA of selected crops. The strategy strived to promote the implementation of activities relating to germplasm conservation, plant breeding and seed delivery systems and fostering linkages between them in order to improve crop productivity and production and livelihoods.

The current National PGRFA Strategy seeks to escalate efforts of the first strategy in terms of broadening the scope to include all PGRFA and all aspects of its management and sustainable use taking into

consideration challenges encountered in the implementation of the previous national strategy and new developments.

CHAPTER 2: SITUATIONAL ANALYSIS

There is a general appreciation of the importance of PGRFA in Zambia, both by government and non-state actors such as seed companies and NGOs involved in agricultural and rural development programmes. There is also an increasing trend among the public to appreciate and promote dietary diversity derived from local food crops. Government's promotion of the crop diversification strategy with the aim of enhancing household and national food and nutrition security is contributing to an increase in crop diversity.

The appreciation of the value and importance of PGRFA is evidenced by measures that have been put in place by the government and other partners and stakeholders. These efforts include commitments made by the government through signing and being a Party to International Agreements related to PGRFA such as the ITPGRFA and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) as well as deliberate programmes put in place and implemented over the years. The need to continue and further increase such efforts is appreciated by most stakeholders and partners especially in view of increased threats to PGRFA and the continued need to scale up sustainable use of PGRFA in order to improve the food and nutrition security of the country.

The revision of the draft national strategy requires a comprehensive situational analysis relating to the existing diversity of PGRFA, effectiveness of programmes or interventions put in place as well as the governance, policy and legislative environment impacting PGRFA management in Zambia. The analysis also includes identification of

threats, challenges encountered and opportunities available to enhance the efficiency of PGRFA management.

2.1 Status of PGRFA Diversity

A range of indigenous, exotic and naturalized plant species and varieties including cereals, legumes, oil crops, root and tubers, fiber, fruit trees, vegetables and plantation crops are cultivated in Zambia. Generally, maize remains a dominant crop cultivated mainly by smallholder farmers across the country. This is largely due to continued government support through a subsidy programme, Farmer Input Support Programme (FISP), for agricultural inputs such as fertilizers and certified seed. In the last five years, the programme has included support for other crops such as sorghum, rice, groundnuts and soybeans, which has contributed to increase in on-farm crop diversity.

An inventory of plant species carried out has indicated that there are about 107 plant species cultivated in Zambia (NBSAP-2, 2015). Out of these plant species, 52% are exotic, 33% are naturalized and 15% are indigenous to Zambia. These crops including exotic and naturalized have undergone adaptation that has led to the generation of unique and valuable crop genetic diversity, which have continued to play an important role in agricultural productivity, are contributing to household food, nutrition, livelihoods security and peace.

Zambia also possesses a wide range of plant genetic resources of Crop Wild Relatives (CWRs) and useful wild plant species. CWRs taxa include those of rice, cowpea, sorghum, millets, a range of cucurbits, kenaf, sesame species, a range of indigenous vegetable species, fodder and forage species, fruit trees and mushrooms that may be semi-cultivated or gathered from the wild. The Second National Strategic Action Plan

for the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Crop Wild Relatives in Zambia identifies a partial checklist of 459 CWR taxa from 59 national priority crops in the country.

While a total of 6,900 accessions of about 40 different crop species are conserved at the National Plant Genetic Resources Centre (NPGRC), diversity occurring on-farm seems to be under threat of erosion and loss due to a number of factors. Major among these is the apparent increase in the use of improved varieties by smallholder farmers, in particular hybrids for maize. The country continues to witness an increase in the number of companies and organizations involved in the development of improved crop varieties, production and marketing of seeds of these varieties. On one hand, this seems to be contributing to a wider genetic diversity especially when development of open pollinated varieties are involved, while on the other it tends to contribute to the narrowing of crop diversity of local farmers' crop varieties as preference is tilted towards hybrid crop varieties by smallholder farmers.

2.2 National Programmes for PGRFA Management

A National Plant Genetic Resources Programme was established in 1989 and included the establishment of the NPGRC or National Genebank, as a unit within the Zambia Agriculture Research Institute (ZARI) under the Ministry of Agriculture. The National Plant Genetic Resources Programme was established as part of the SADC Plant Genetic Resources Network Programme, with support from the NORDIC countries over a twenty-year period, that ended in 2012.

The National Programme on Plant Genetic Resources was designed to ensure the conservation and sustainable use of the country's crop genepool, underpinning food and nutrition security. This was to be

achieved by undertaking PGRFA collection missions, preserving and maintenance of the collected material samples of PGRFA, description and value addition of conserved PGRFA through genetic characterization, information documentation and distribution of germplasm to users at national, regional and international levels.

Initially, the NPGRC prioritized major traditional food crops, of orthodox seed type, in line with the priorities of the Ministry of Agriculture. The prioritization of crops was influenced by the availability of facilities for conservation of crops with orthodox seeds.

2.2.1 Inventories and Collections

Over the past 30 years, a number of collection missions covering almost the entire country were undertaken (Figure 1). Most of these collection missions, that were funded by the NORDIC countries, were of multicrop nature, targeting a wide range of local crop varieties. These germplasm collections constitute the major part of the current total collection held in the Genebank. A proportion of PGRFA collections conserved in the national genebank was repatriated from Consultative Group of International Agricultural Research (CGIAR) genebanks and obtained from breeders in the local public research stations.

There were also collections targeting crop wild relatives (CWRs) undertaken in later years in collaboration with international organisations, including International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Bioversity International, International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) and Global Crop Diversity Trust (GCDT). CWRs species that were collected included sorghum, rice and cowpea.

Due to a number of challenges, including remoteness and inaccessibility of certain areas, some areas were not covered during these collection missions. Vegetatively propagated crop species and those with recalcitrant seeds were also not collected.

Figure 1: Map showing germplasm collection areas in Zambia

2.2.2 Maintenance and Management of Plant Genetic Resources

Conservation of plant genetic resources aims at maintenance of the genetic integrity of the available genetic diversity so that this can be used both at present and in future crop research and development. Two main approaches have been used for maintenance of PGRFA in Zambia, ex-situ and in situ conservation.

Ex situ Approaches

Two approaches of ex situ conservation have been employed, storage of seed samples in a Genebank facility and maintenance of living plants in the field. The approach of seed storage starts with drying seed samples to moisture content of less than 7%, followed by packing in aluminium foil bag and hermetically sealing the bag before placing them for storage in deep freezers operating at -20° C. The use of deep freezers system as opposed to cold room is advantageous in that when one unit is non-functional, other units will remain available for use. However, there has to be a replacement plan of deep freezer units so that replacements of individual units can be effected without much delay. In order to maintain the temperature regimes for germplasm conservation, there is also need to ensure continuous electricity supply as there have been times when frequent power outages were experienced at the NPGRC rendering deep freezers non- functional. Although a generator set was procured to be on standby to provide power during times when the main supply is not available, the major challenge was often the non-availability of fuel to run it.

The storage conditions of temperature and humidity used must be good enough for long term maintenance of viable seed. The viability of seed samples maintained in the Gene bank is monitored through germination testing. Although the NPGRC is in the position to carry out basic germination testing, its capacity to handle full scale viability monitoring remains inadequate.

The other ex situ approach that has been used to a lesser extent is the field Genebank or field collection. This has been used to conserve cassava and sweet potato clones. The challenge faced by this method has been inadequate moisture and the cold condition during the off season leading to loss of plants. The NPGRC does not have facilities

such as glasshouses and screen houses which provide better and secure environments for the management of PGRFA as live plants.

As part of ex situ methods, the NPGRC has periodically grown PGRFA samples for purposes of regenerating them when viability has gone down below a set threshold (85% viability for most field and horticultural crops) and increasing seed samples for distribution to users requesting for PGRFA.

There is a total of about 6,900 accessions of seed samples maintained in the national genebank as an active collection against the initial number of 1479 accessions in 1989 covering about 40 different crop species recorded in Zambia (Table 1). This indicates an increment in number of accessions by more than four folds since the establishment of the NPGRC. In addition, there are also 50 clonal accessions of cassava (*Manihot esculentus*) and 260 accessions of sweet potato (*Ipomeae batata*) which are maintained as living plants in the field collection. livingstone potato (*Plectranthus esculentus*) collections were once maintained in the field collection but were lost due to lack of functional irrigation system.

Table 1. Number of germplasm accessions conserved in the national Genebank

Crop plants	Number of accessions
African eggplant	19
Amaranth	194
Bambara groundnuts	203
Beans	170
Cantaloupe	52
Castor bean	68

Brassica	60
Cleome	28
Cotton	159
Cow peas	494
Cucurbits	649
Ethiopian kale	76
False Roselle	86
Finger millet	383
Groundnuts	515
Lablab	1
Lupins	1
Maize	644
Momordica	2
Mungbean	3
Okra	235
Pawpaw	1
Pearl millet	626
Peas	15
Pepper	31
Pigeon peas	124
Rice	293
Roselle	43
Sesame	73
Sesbania	18
Sorghum	953
Soya beans	2
Spider plant	66
Sunflower	70

Sweet potato	260
Tephrosia	17
Tobacco	14
Tomato	42
Velvet beans	9
West Indian Gherkin	1
Wheat	17
Wild cowpea	53
Wild finger millet	65
Wild Rice	65
Grand total	6,900

In situ and On-farm Management Approaches

The *in-situ* method as a strategy for the conservation of PGRFA of wild plant species and CWRs nature has been initiated by the NPGRC. Some of the useful wild plants and CWRs have been conserved in situ through wildlife protected area system and forestry reserves which fall under the mandates of the departments of National Parks and Wildlife under the Ministry of Tourism and Forestry Department under the Ministry of Green Economy and Environment. The management and conservation of these wild plant resources are influenced by a number of policies, legislation and strategies being administered by different line Ministries.

On farm management of PGRFA has been employed by the NPGRC and NGOs mainly aimed at supporting smallholder farmers and farming communities to continue playing their role in the development and conservation of crop diversity found on their farmlands and within the farming systems in which they have evolved. The activities supported include strengthening local seed systems based on farmers' varieties,

broadening the local crop diversity through seed fairs and community seed banks, involvement of farmers in participatory plant breeding and awareness creation on the importance and value of PGRFA.

Some programmes and activities regarding on-farm management of PGRFA have been undertaken by the NPGRC and NGOs such as CTD and PELUM in parts of Northern, Muchinga, Southern, Eastern, Central and Lusaka provinces. Crops targeted under these interventions are mainly finger millet, maize, cowpea, groundnuts, sorghum and cucurbits.

Adding Value to PGRFA through Characterization and Preliminary Evaluation

The NPGRC undertakes agro-morphological characterisation and preliminary evaluation to add value to the conserved PGRFA. Agro-morphological characterisation involves growing out accessions in the field and collecting or recording data on selected morphological characters and agronomic attributes. There has been an increase in the capacity for molecular characterization following the acquisition of facilities and training of staff. However, utilization levels of these facilities is low due to inadequate funding for operational costs.

A total of 2,669 accessions have so far been morphologically characterised based on descriptors developed by Bioversity International. The number of accessions characterised represent about 40% of the total number of collections maintained in the Genebank. Most of the accessions characterized are of sorghum, maize, groundnuts, pigeon pea, bambara nuts, cucurbits, rice, cowpea and pearl millet (Table 2). There is, however, still a backlog of PGRFA collections yet to be characterised.

Table 2. Number of conserved germplasm accessions characterized for each crop species

Crop	No. of accessions
Maize	250
Sorghum	571
Pearl millet	94
Finger millet	483
Cowpea	496
Beans	228
Bambara nuts	217
Ground nuts	130
Rice	150
Pigeon pea	50
Total	2669

Distribution and utilisation of PGRFA

Germplasm accessions have been distributed in response to requests from both institutions within the country and those from other countries. To date, a total of 415 have been distributed to user institutions (Table 3). From this it can be seen that the distribution of PGRFA collections has been low, indicating that there has also been low utilisation of these collections in crop research and development. The low utilization could be attributed to the low numbers of accessions that have been described.

Table 3. Germplasm accessions distributed by institutions to date

Institution	Crop	Number of accessions
University of Kwazulu	Maize	280
	Cowpea	30
University of Zambia	Cowpea	15
	Rice	30
International Rice Research Institute	Crop wild relatives of rice	15
Mulungushi University	Groundnuts	15
	Bambara nuts	20
	Maize	10
Total		415

2.3 Threats and Challenges

There are a number of factors that pose threats to PGRFA, either in collections maintained in the genebank or that existing on farmlands of traditional farming systems of smallholder farmers. PGRFA collections in the genebank are threatened by unstable storage conditions largely due to unreliable electricity power supply and limitation of storage space due to breakdown of freezers. Crop diversity on farm is at risk of erosion and loss from threats arising from occurrence of droughts and floods, disease and insect pest outbreaks. The loss of diversity of crop wild relatives and useful wild species is threatened by degazetting of protected forests for human settlement and commercial agricultural development for monocropping, burning, clearing of vegetation for agricultural, excessive use of herbicides and unsustainable harvesting methods.

Threats caused by drought and floods is particularly pronounced in agro ecological regions I and II, causing disruptions to the smallholder

farming systems and their livelihoods. These threats are likely to increase in the face of climate change. This has led farmers in these areas to shift from the cultivation of some crops such as maize to more drought tolerant crops like sorghum and pearl millet. The situation has also led to reduced varietal diversity within crops as farmers tend to plant earlier maturing varieties that fit into the shorter growing seasons.

2.4 International Agreements and Action Plans Relevant to PGRFA

There are a number of International Agreements relevant to PGRFA to which Zambia is party. These include the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and its protocols, the Nagoya Protocol on access and benefit sharing and the Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety, International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (ITPGRFA), United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), RAMSAR Convention on Wetlands of International Importance, Trade-Related Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) Agreement under the World Trade Organisation (WTO) and the rolling Global Plan of Action (GPA) for PGRFA.

Zambia has domesticated these agreements and conventions to varying degrees. However, the extent to which the country has domesticated these agreements is generally low.

The CBD, RAMSAR Convention and the UNFCCC, whose implementation is led by the Ministry of Green Economy and Environment are being domesticated through a number of existing policies and legislation. For example, the CBD is being domesticated by the implementation of the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP), the UNFCCC through implementation of the provisions of the Paris Agreement, the implementation of the Nationally

Determined Contribution and the National Policy on Climate Change. The RAMSAR Convention is being domesticated through the implementation of the National Wetlands Policy. The Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety is being domesticated through the 2003 Policy on Biosafety and the 2007 Biosafety Act. The Nagoya Protocol which has not been fully domesticated has so far been implemented through the adoption of the legislation for its implementation and putting in place an institutional framework. What remains is to finalize the regulations for access and benefit sharing from the use of genetic resources and traditional knowledge.

The ITPGRFA is at the centre of PGRFA management and sustainable use and equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of their use, in harmony with the CBD for sustainable agriculture and food security. The provisions of the Treaty include actions that governments should take to conserve, provide access and utilize PGRFA. Key components of this Treaty include a global multilateral mechanism for access and benefit sharing (Articles 10 to 13) and the Farmers' Rights (Article 9), which provides what the rights of farmers are and therefore measures that should be taken at national level for their realization. Although there are some policies and legislations that may be applied towards the domestication of the ITPGRFA in Zambia, no specific policy and legislative measures have been put in place to support the realization of farmers' rights as outlined in the ITPGRFA. Among existing legislation that could be applied for this purpose is the *'Protection of Traditional Knowledge, Genetic Resources and Expressions of Folklore Act. of 2016'*. This law has great potential to support the realization of farmers' rights.

2.5 Governance and Institutional Arrangements

The Ministry of Agriculture through ZARI shoulders the main responsibility for implementing the national programme for the conservation and management of PGRFA. This includes the coordination role and implementation of key activities pertaining to the conservation and sustainable utilization of PGRFA of cultivated crops and their crop wild relatives. ZARI, houses the NPGRC or national genebank, and a number of commodity based research programmes whose main objectives is the development and improvement of crop varieties for increased crop productivity and production. The overall objective and mandate of the NPGRC is the conservation of the country's genepool of plant genetic resources for food and agriculture and facilitation of access to these genetic resources for use in crop variety development and improvement. Specifically, the NPGRC is responsible for undertaking PGRFA collection, conservation, characterization, information documentation and distribution of germplasm to users at national, regional and international levels.

Some stakeholders have observed that the current institutional arrangement for the implementation of the national PGRFA programme is not adequate. The NPGRC is specifically responsible for coordinating the programme and implementation of key activities and exists as a unit within ZARI. This arrangement is not favourable for the attraction of funding support both internally and externally. It is desired that the status of the NPGRC be elevated and its mandate broadened in order to create adequate capacity to do more work, including research to support sustainable use of PGRFA.

ZARI collaborates with other public institutions and NGOs in different aspects of PGRFA management. These include the Seed Control and Certification Institute (SCCI), Department of Agriculture (DoA), Cotton Development Trust (CDT) and Golden Valley Agricultural Research Trust (GART). Though at a low level, collaboration with these institutions and organisations has been critical in the implementation of activities for the conservation and sustainable use of PGRFA. Budgetary constraint is partly responsible for this low level of collaboration.

The National Plant Genetic Resources Committee (NPGRCom), whose membership is drawn from different stakeholder institutions and organisations, that are responsible for providing policy and technical oversight in the implementation of the PGRFA programme was established as part of the implementation arrangement for the national programme on PGRFA. This committee, has in the last 10 years not been consistently playing its role mainly due to budgetary constraints. The Ministry of Agriculture is part of the National Biodiversity Committee which has a role of coordinating implementation of biodiversity programmes and activities in the country.

2.6 National Policies, Strategies and Legislation Relevant to PGRFA Management

The policies and legislation that may be used to support the management of PGRFA in Zambia are found in different institutions across a number of sectors.

The overarching policies for management of biodiversity and biosafety are under the Ministry of Green Economy and Environment (MGEE). These include the National Climate Change Policy of 2016, National Wetlands Policy, Forestry Policy of 2014 and the Forests Act No. 4 of 2015 and the National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP).

The specific policies, plans and programmes that relate to the management of PGRFA are under the Ministry of Agriculture. The key policy being the Second National Agriculture Policy (SNAP) 2016-2020. The main objective of the SNAP is to facilitate and support the development of a sustainable and competitive agricultural sector that assures food and nutrition security at national and household levels and maximizes the sector's contribution to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The SNAP does not have adequate provisions to support the management of PGRFA. In this regard, there will be need to include specific provisions for the management of PGRFA in the next review of the SNAP.

Other key policies, programmes and legislations impacting on PGRFA management are found in the Ministry of Commerce, Trade and Industry (MCTI), Ministry of Technology and Science and Ministry of Water Development, Sanitation and Environment Protection (MWDSEP).

Under the MCTI there is the National Intellectual Policy, which provides direction in development of intellectual property rights for different sectors. The Ministry, through the Patents and Companies Registration Agency (PACRA), also administers the Protection of Traditional Knowledge, Genetic Resources and Expressions of Folklore Act No. 16 of 2016 which regulates access and benefit sharing from the use of genetic resources and traditional knowledge. The MWDSEP regulates environmental management through the Environmental Management Act while the Ministry of Technology and Science regulates issues on science and technology.

There are a number of strategies and legislations or laws that have been put in place to support the implementation of the above policies. Under the MLNR the key strategy is the NBSAP, which is a key national instrument for implementing the provisions of CBD, including those

that relate to the conservation and sustainable use of PGRFA and protection of associated traditional knowledge. Under the MCTI, the key legislation is the Protection of Traditional Knowledge, Genetic Resources and Expressions of Folklore Act No. 16 of 2016. This Act has the potential to provide for the implementation of some provisions of Farmers' Rights under the ITPGRFA.

CHAPTER 3: SCOPE AND RATIONALE

3.1 Scope

The National PGRFA Strategy covers all PGRFA occurring in the country and includes plant species that are cultivated, CWRs and wild plant species gathered for food and agricultural uses. The strategy addresses management and conservation of PGRFA held as *ex situ* collections, those being managed and utilized on-farm and those existing in *in situ* conditions. The strategy extends its coverage to PGRFA under development, including released improved crop varieties.

3.2 Rationale

Efforts have been made in the past to develop a national PGRFA strategy for Zambia. This includes the FAO supported and SPGRC coordinated draft national strategy developed in 2013, which was never finalized and adopted. This draft was also limited to addressing few specific crop species. The other national PGRFA strategy, developed and adopted in 2016 and supported by Bioversity International through a Darwin Initiative project is specifically addressing the conservation and sustainable use of priority crop wild relatives. From the foregoing, it is clear that Zambia has not had a comprehensive and holistic National Strategy covering all PGRFA. For both draft strategies, implementation of strategic actions has been inadequate. It is therefore felt imperative to review the draft PGRFA strategy with a view to develop a comprehensive and holistic national PGRFA strategy. There is a renewed realization and appreciation of the need to step up efforts for the conservation and sustainable use of the country's PGRFA in order to increase its contribution to household and national food and nutrition security.

CHAPTER 4: STRATEGIC DIRECTION

Zambia's PGRFA genepool is of great importance and value as it forms a foundation for food and nutrition security, agricultural and rural development, and resilience to environmental and climate shocks. It is therefore imperative that a strategic plan that provides a vision, goal, objectives and strategic interventions covering all aspects of PGRFA management and sustainable use is put in place.

4.1 Vision

A vibrant and well-coordinated PGRFA conservation and sustainable use agenda that is positively contributing to climate change resilience, increased food and nutrition security and sovereignty, agricultural development and national economic prosperity.

4.2 Goal

PGRFA is optimally conserved, sustainably used and contributes to improved livelihoods of all Zambians under an enabling legal and institutional environment that promotes research and capacity development.

4.3 Strategic Objectives

Main objective

To promote the development of an effective and efficient system for the conservation and sustainable use of PGRFA.

Specific objectives

The national PGRFA will be implemented under five strategic objectives.

Strategic Objective (SO) 1: Strengthen the conservation and enhance the sustainable use of plant genetic resources.

Strategic objective (SO) 2: Provide an enabling legal and institutional framework for the management of PGRFA

Strategic Objective (SO) 3: Strengthen institutional capacities for promoting research and development in PGRFA

Strategic Objective (SO) 4: Increase/strengthen capacities of stakeholders including local communities, private and public sectors to ensure their effective participation in management of PGRFA

Strategic Objective (SO) 5: Increase/strengthen capability for knowledge management and information dissemination to enhance appreciation of the value, and increase access, benefit sharing and sustainable use of PGRFA

4.4 Strategic Intervention Areas and Actions

4.4.1 Strategic objective 1: Strengthen and enhance conservation and sustainable use of PGRFA

In order to achieve this strategic objective, the following interventions will be implemented:

Strategic Intervention Area 1 – Enhancing *ex situ* conservation of PGRFA.

Strategic Intervention Area 2 - Strengthening on farm management of PGRFA.

Strategic intervention Area 3 – Strengthening in situ conservation of CWRs and wild plants

Strategic Intervention Area 4 - Promotion of sustainable use of PGRFA.

Strategic Intervention Area 5 - Strengthening the Information Management System of the ex-situ collections.

4.4.2 Strategic objective 2

Availing an enabling legal and institutional framework for management of PGRFA

In order to achieve this strategic objective, the following interventions will be implemented:

Strategic Intervention Area 1 – Development of legislative and institutional framework for the implementation of Farmers’ Rights.

Strategic Intervention Area 2 – Development of framework for equitable sharing of benefits arising from the use of PGRFA

Strategic Intervention Area 3- Development of mechanisms of recognition, protection and commercialization of farmers’ varieties.

Strategic Intervention Area 4 - Documentation of PGRFA related traditional knowledge.

4.4.3 Strategic Objective 3

Strengthening the enabling environment for promoting research and development in PGRFA

In order to achieve this strategic objective, the following interventions will be implemented:

Strategic Intervention Area 1 – Research and development enhancement and expansion of PGRFA including cultivated and wild plants and their uses.

Strategic Intervention Area 2 – Pre breeding and production of early generation seed

4.4.4 Strategic Objective 4

Strengthening partnerships and collaboration in the management of PGRFA

In order to achieve this strategic objective, the following interventions will be implemented:

Strategic Intervention Area 1 - Enhancing capacity for participation of farmers and local communities in the management of PGRFA.

Strategic Intervention Area 2 – Enhancing capacity of technical staff involved in PGRFA development and management.

Strategic Intervention Area 3 - Enhancing capacity of decision makers for better understanding and appreciation of PGRFA issues.

Strategic Intervention Area 4 – Supporting platform/mechanism that enhance multi-sectoral (public, private and NGOs) participation or involvement

4.4.5 Strategic Objective 5

Increase/strengthen capability for knowledge management and information dissemination to enhance appreciation, access and sustainable use of PGRFA. In order to achieve this strategic objective, the following interventions will be implemented:

Strategic Intervention Area 1 - Strengthening the Information Management System, packaging, documentation and dissemination.

Strategic Intervention Area 2- Development of a communication plan to facilitate awareness raising and information sharing on the National Strategy for PGRFA.

CHAPTER 5: IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

The implementation of the National Strategy on PGRFA will largely be the responsibility of the Ministry responsible for agriculture through ZARI, working closely with key stakeholder institutions from the public, private, NGOs and quasi-Governmental sectors. Participating institutions based on their mandates and specialization will have specific responsibilities during the implementation of the strategy.

5.1 Coordination and Collaboration

The Ministry responsible for agriculture, through ZARI will play a leading and coordinating role in the implementation of the National Strategy on PGRFA. ZARI, which is the country's largest publicly funded research institution, will also take up specific roles covering the management of PGRFA collections held at the national genebank, genetic enhancement leading to crop variety development, on-farm management of PGRFA, regeneration and multiplication of seed samples, mobilization and conservation of the PGRFA, characterization of conserved germplasm and their distribution to different users.

Given the complexity of PGRFA activities arising from the fact that they cover various divergent sectors, there is need for coordination both horizontally between different ministries and sectors and vertically between technical staff and policy-makers within institutions playing particular roles in the implementation of the strategy. It is important to involve representatives of various stakeholder institutions in the implementation of the programme so as to maximize the number of actors in the programme, increase the sense of ownership of the programme, obtain a variety of ideas on the needs to be addressed and to build a constituency for PGRFA that will help generate political and practical support for the programme. An effective national PGRFA

programme will require efficient coordination as well as a high degree of collaboration between relevant stakeholder institutions.

The implementation of this strategy will need to be guided by a National Steering Committee for PGRFA that has representation from key national stakeholder institutions including Government line Ministries, Non-Governmental organizations, Academia and Quasi-Governmental institutions. The National Steering Committee will be responsible for policy guidance and broader coordination of PGRFA Programmes.

The following institutions and organizations will be represented in the National Steering Committee covering research, training, seeds, extension, natural resources and environment, regulatory and policy:

1. **Research** (ZARI, NISIR, UNZA, CBU)
2. **Training** (UNZA, CBU, NRDC, MU, KATC, ZAAB)
3. **Seeds** (SCCI, ZASTA); **Civil society** (PELUM, FIAN International, CTDT, ZNFU)
4. **Extension** (DoA, ZNFU, BCN, CTDT, NUSFAZ); **Media** (NAIS)
5. Ministries responsible for **Agriculture, Science, Lands and Natural Resources** (ZEMA, DNPW, THPAZ);
6. **Forestry genetic resources** (Forestry Department)
7. **National Food and Nutrition Commission** (NFNC)
8. **Regulatory bodies** (ZEMA, SCCI, PACRA, NBA)

Other participating institutions not represented on the steering Committee but could be co-opted as members as the case may arise will include:

1. Golden Valley Agriculture Research Trust (GART)
2. Cotton Development Trust (CDT)
3. SADC Plant Genetic Resources Centre (SPGRC)
4. Ministry of Finance (MoF)
5. Civil society organizations and NGOS
6. Ministry of Justice (MoJ)
7. Mundawanga Botanic Gardens
8. Chiefs and Traditional Affairs

Annex 1 provides a list of participating institutions and organizations and specifies their main roles in the implementation of the strategy.

5.2 Implementation Matrix

The implementation matrix as illustrated in Table 4, includes activity and time scheduling, assigning responsibilities and setting targets under each of the strategic objectives.

Table 4. Implementation matrix of the National Strategy for PGRFA

Strategic Objective 1: To strengthen and enhance conservation and sustainable use				
Activity	Target	Responsible institution	Start date	End date
1.1 Identify conservation gaps	All existing conservation gaps	ZARI, DNPW, Forestry Dept.	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2023
1.2 undertake gap-filling collections	500 accessions	ZARI, DNPW, Forestry Dept.	April, 2023	April, 2025
1.3 upgrade PGRFA conservation facilities	100 % of facilities upgraded	ZARI	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2023
1.4 strengthen on-farm management of PGRFA	10 community seed banks established	ZARI, PELUM, KATC, CTD, Green Living Movement	Jan, 2023	June, 2027
1.5 Undertake pre breeding or germplasm enhancement	Novel genes for adaptation to biotic and abiotic stress identified in conserved PGRFA	UNZA, ZARI, NISIR	Mar 2023	Dec 2025
1.6 enhance participatory plant breeding	At least 500 farmers trained in participatory plant breeding	ZARI, UNZA, GART, KACT, PELUM, CTD	Jan,2023	Dec, 2027
1.7 undertake sustainable use of PGRFA	90% of NPGRC collections characterized and evaluated	ZARI, UNZA, GART	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2026

1.8 undertake inventory and documentation of PGRFA	data and information on all PGRFA collections documented and publicly accessible	ZARI, UNZA, DNPW	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2027
Strategic Objective 2: To provide for the enabling legal and institutional framework for management of PGRFA				
2.1 domesticate the ITPGRFA, including Farmers' Rights	A legal framework is put in place by end of 2024	PPD, ZARI, MoJ, CSOs & NGOs, KATC, PELUM	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2026
2.3 establish farmers' varieties registration	A framework for farmers' varieties registration agreed and adopted by 2026	PPD, ZARI, MoJ, CSOs & NGOs	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2027
2.4 legalise the informal seed system	Legal framework for the operation of the informal seed system in place by 2026	PPD, ZARI, MoJ, CSOs & NGOs	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2027
Strategic Objective 3: Strengthening the enabling environment for promoting research and development in PGRFA				
3.1 Strengthen the use of gene mapping	50% of PGRFA collections genome sequenced	ZARI, UNZA, SCCI	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2027
3.2 Strengthen capacity in plant systematics	20 scientists trained in plant systematics	UNZA	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2027

3.3 Strengthen capacity in seed technology	50 scientists trained in seed technology	SCCI, UNZA, ZARI, NRDC	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2027
Strategic Objective 4: Enhancing capacity for the participation of local community, technical staff and decision makers' participation in management of PGRFA				
4.1 Enhance the capacity of farmers and local communities in the management of PGRFA	2,500 farmers trained in PGRFA management	ZARI, CSOs, NGOs	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2027
4.2 strengthen the capacity of technical staff involved in PGRFA development and management	150 technical staff trained in PGRFA development and management	ZARI, UNZA, SCCI, MLNR, NRDC	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2027
4.3 enhance the capacity of decision makers for better understanding and appreciation of PGRFA issues	25 training workshops conducted	ZARI, UNZA, SCCI, MLNR	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2027

Strategic Objective 5: Increase/strengthen capability for knowledge management and information dissemination to enhance appreciation, access and sustainable use of PGRFA

5.1 store, package and document information on PGRFA	An effective information system for PGRFA is deployed by end of 2026	ZARI	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2027
5.2 develop a communication strategy to increase awareness about PGRFA and its value	A communication strategy is developed and in use by 2026	ZARI, CSOs	Jan, 2023	Dec, 2027

CHAPTER 6: MONITORING AND EVALUATION

The implementation of the national strategy for PGRFA requires a mechanism to track progress towards achieving set targets and optimizing use of human, financial and other resources. Such a mechanism will also provide a periodical review of the implementation modalities in order to address changing needs and priorities as necessary. To be able to track the progress of implementation, there is need to develop and put in place a monitoring and evaluation system as an integral part of this strategy. The M&E system will also be used as a mechanism to adjust priorities, targets and measures in line with the national needs.

The monitoring and evaluation framework is essential to determine the progress of implementation of the strategies and activities in order to achieve the set strategic objectives. This will provide the basis for evaluating the effectiveness of the interventions and actions taken, facilitate early detection of emerging problems, record changes over time, make informed decisions and adjustments and plan ongoing management activities.

The M&E framework will include agreed verifiable performance indicators and targets, provide practical recommendations, lessons learnt for updating, revising and expansion. The M&E framework will also provide data and information capturing templates to be used during regular monitoring exercises by a multi-disciplinary team led by ZARI through the NPGRC. Agencies involved in the implementation of programmes and activities will report annually the implementation progress using the performance indicators in Table 5. Midterm review for M&E will also be carried out in 2024 in order to track progress, quality and impact of activities undertaken by various partners in the implementation of PGRFA strategy. The final review or end line survey will also be carried out in 2026.

Table 5. Performance indicators for the planned activities for each of the strategic objectives of the National Strategy for PGRFA

Strategic Objective 1: To strengthen and enhance conservation and sustainable use					
Strategic action	Baseline	Target	Time line	Indicators	Responsible institution
1.1 Identify conservation gaps	No gap analysis in place	All existing conservation gaps	2023–2024	Number of gaps identified	ZARI, DNPW, Forestry Dept.
1.2 Undertake gap-filling collections	Not all areas and PGRFA collected.	500 accessions	2023–2025	Number of accessions collected	ZARI, DNPW, Forestry Dept.
1.3 Upgrade PGRFA ex situ conservation facilities	Limited ex situ conservation facilities	100 % of facilities upgraded	2023–2024	Development of specifications Procurement procedures and construction works	ZARI
1.4 Establish community banks	4 existing community seed banks	5 community seed banks established	2023–2025	Number of community seed banks established	ZARI, KATC, PELUM

1.5 Enhance participatory plant breeding	Less than 100 farmers trained in participatory breeding	At least 500 farmers trained in participatory plant breeding	2023- 2027	Number of farmers trained, disaggregated by sex and age	ZARI, UNZA, GART, KATC, PELUM
1.6 Undertake germplasm enhancement or pre breeding of PGRFA	No systematic pre breeding has been undertaken	60% of PGRFA collections pre bred or enhanced	2023-2025	% of conserved germplasm accessions pre bred	
1.7 Undertake characterization and evaluation of PGRFA	About 50 percent of PGRFA collections characterised	90% of NPGRC collections characterized and evaluated	2023–2026	% of conserved germplasm accessions characterized and evaluated	ZARI, UNZA, GART
1.8 Undertake inventory and documentation of PGRFA and maintenance of information system	Limited documentation of PGRFA	Data and information on all PGRFA collections documented and publicly accessible	2023–2027	Inventory /Database produced	ZARI,UNZA, DNPW

Strategic Objective 2: To provide for the enabling legal and institutional framework for management of PGRFA

<p>2.1 Develop the legislative framework for implementation of Farmers' Rights</p>	<p>No legislative framework for implementation of Farmers' Rights</p>	<p>A legal framework is put in place by end of 2026</p>	<p>2023–2026</p>	<p>Number of position papers produced Number of farmer groups consulted Number of policies reviewed and developed</p>	<p>ZARI, PPD, MoJ, CSOs & NGOs</p>
<p>2.2 Develop mechanisms and farmer organisations for implementation of Farmers' Rights</p>	<p>Limited involvement of farmer organisations in implementation of Farmers' Rights</p>	<p>Increase in number of farmer organisation involved in the implementation of farmers' Rights.</p>	<p>2023-2027</p>	<p>Number of farmer organisations supported and involved in implementation of Farmers' Rights</p>	<p>ZARI, PPD, CSOs & NGOs</p>

2.3 Review or develop mechanisms for enhancing equitable sharing of benefits arising from use of PGRFA	No framework for equitable sharing of benefits arising from use of PGRFA	A legal framework is in place by 2026	2023-2026	A legal framework for equitable sharing of benefits arising from use of PGRFA in place	ZARI, PPD, MoJ, CSOs & NGOs
2.4 establish register for farmers' varieties	No Farmers' varieties register in place	A framework for farmers' varieties registration agreed and adopted by 2026	2023-2027	A national catalogue of farmers' varieties developed A register for Farmers' varieties in place	ZARI, PPD, MoJ, CSOs & NGOs
2.5 Develop mechanisms for legalization of the informal seed system	No legal system for informal seed system	Legal framework for the operation of the informal seed system in place by 2026	2023-2027	Seed quality assurance standards for farmers' varieties 100 farmers trained in quality seed production, disaggregated by sex and age	ZARI, PPD, MoJ, CSOs & NGOs

2.6 Recognition and protection of traditional knowledge systems	No recognition and protection of traditional knowledge systems	1 National database for traditional knowledge related to PGRFA developed	2023-2027	Databases developed	ZARI, NBA, PPD, MoJ, CSOs & NGOs
	No referral sequence database in place to effectively regulate genetic engineering	1 National Digital Sequencing Information System established			

Strategic Objective 3: Strengthening the enabling environment for promoting research and development in PGRFA					
3.1 Strengthen the use of gene mapping	No collections are genome sequenced	50% of PGRFA collections genome sequenced	2023–2027	Number of accessions sequenced	ZARI, UNZA, SCCI
3.2 Training of staff in plant systematics	No new scientists trained in recent past	20 scientists trained in plant systematics	2023–2027	Number of scientists trained in plant systematics, disaggregated by gender and sex Number of conserved PGRFA species fully identified	ZARI, UNZA
3.3 Training of staff in seed technology	No new scientists trained in seed technology in recent past	50 scientists trained in seed technology	2023–2027	Number of scientists trained in seed technology, disaggregated by sex and age	SCCI, UNZA, ZARI, KATC

Strategic Objective 4: Enhancing capacity for the participation of local community, technical staff and decision makers' participation in management of PGRFA

4.1 Enhance the capacity of farmers and local communities in the management of PGRFA	No farmers formally trained in the management of PGRFA and participatory plant breeding at local community level	2,500 farmers trained in PGRFA management and participatory plant breeding (50% are women farmers)	2023–2027	Number of farmers trained, disaggregated by sex and age	ZARI, CSOs, NGOs, KATC
4.2 strengthen the capacity of technical staff involved in PGRFA development and management	Lacking advanced skills in PGRFA management and use	150 technical staff trained in advanced skills for PGRFA development and management	2023–2027	Number of technical staff acquired advanced PGRFA skills, disaggregated by sex and age	ZARI, UNZA, SCCI, MLNR, NRDC

	Limited coverage of PGRFA in curricula	PGRFA mainstreamed into national education curricula at secondary and higher education levels	2023-2026	Number of training programmes incorporating PGRFA	ZARI, UNZA, SCCI, MLNR, NRDC
4.3 enhance the capacity of decision makers for better understanding and appreciation of PGRFA issues	Limited awareness of PGRFA at policy maker level	25 training workshops conducted	2023–2027	Number of awareness workshops for policy makers held	ZARI, UNZA, SCCI, MLNR

Strategic Objective 5: increase/strengthen capability for knowledge management and information dissemination to enhance appreciation, access and sustainable use of PGRFA					
5.1 store, package and document information on PGRFA	Few publications	An effective information system for PGRFA is deployed by end of 2026	2023–2027	Number of publications	ZARI
5.2 develop a communication strategy to increase awareness about PGRFA and its value	No PGRFA communication plan in place	A communication strategy is developed and in use by 2026	2023–2027	Communication plan in place	ZARI
5.3 Holding of the national PGRFA dissemination conference	No PGRFA conference	1 dissemination conference/workshop on PGRFA held	2025	Number of conference reports	ZARI

CHAPTER 7: RESOURCE MOBILIZATION

7.1 Funding and financial resources

Finances for the implementation of the strategy for PGRFA in the country will need to be mobilized from a wide range of sources. It is expected that the core funding sources for carrying out activities that directly lead to establishment and strengthening the implementation arrangement will be provided by government, supported by cooperating partners. Funding for some of the planned activities aimed at strengthening the conservation of PGRFA will be sourced from development partners or donors, including FAO, the Alliance of Bioversity International and CIAT and the Benefit Sharing Fund of the International Treaty for Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture. Cooperating partners such as the Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (SIDA) provide funding support for activities that contribute to sustainable use and ultimately contributing to improving food and nutrition security and livelihoods.

The proposed budget estimates for implementing this strategy over a five-year period is provided in Table 6 and is expected to total **ZMW19,725,000**. The total cost for the first year of implementation of the strategy is **ZMW5,440,000**.

7.2 Funding sources

The means to raise funding to implement the strategy will include lobbying government to increase budgetary allocation for the lead institution and to negotiate inclusion of budgets to support PGRFA programmes and activities in partnership with collaborating institutions. In addition to annual government budgetary allocation and supplementary support from cooperating partners, the lead

institution in partnership with other institutions will collaborate in regular joint project proposal development to respond to various funding calls, open competitive grants, bilateral cooperating partner grants and multilateral partners, relevant to conservation and sustainable use of PGRFA.

Other specific sources of funding to support conservation and sustainable use of PGRFA include the CGIAR (ICRISAT, CIMMYT, IITA, ICARDA, IRRI), Swiss Development Cooperation (SDC), Norwegian Agency for Development Cooperation (NORAD) and German Development Agency (GIZ). Much of the potential sources of funding are competitive, therefore the lead institution with collaborating partners will need to establish an arrangement for joint proposal development mechanisms to fully participate in project grant calls that address aspects of PGRFA.

Table 6. Budget (in ZMW) for the implementation of the National Strategy for PGRFA

Strategic objective 1: Strengthen and enhance conservation and sustainable use						
Activities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5	Total
Identification of conservation gaps	25,000	0	0	0	0	25,000
Gap filling collection	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	250,000
Strengthening on-farm management of PGRFA	60,000	60,000	60,000	60,000	60,000	300,000
Participatory plant breeding	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	150,000
Sustainable use of PGRFA	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	10,000	50,000
Inventory and documentation of PGRFA	10,000	50,000	5,000	5,000	5,000	75,000
Characterization and evaluation	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	30,000	150,000
Pre-breeding activities	20,000	20,000	20,000	20,000	20,000	100,000
Production of breeder and foundation seed	20,000	20,000	20,000	20,000	20,000	100,000
Subtotal	255,000	270,000	225,000	225,000	225,000	1,200,000

Strategic objective 2: Legal and institutional framework for management of PGRFA						
Develop the legislative framework for implementation of Farmers' Rights	50,000	150,000	0	0	0	200,000
Develop mechanisms for implementation of ITPGRFA including Farmers' Rights	200,000	150,000	0	0	0	350,000
Establish mechanism for implementation access and benefit sharing provisions of the ITPGRFA	50,000	150,000	50,000	0	0	250,000
Establish system for farmer variety registration and its implementation	50,000	150,000	0	0	0	200,000
Establish register for farmers' varieties	100,000	20,000	20,000	20,000	20,000	180,000
Recognition and protection of traditional knowledge systems	10,000	50,000	0	0	0	60,000
Review of seed laws to accommodate informal seed systems	50,000	150,000	50,000	0	0	250,000
Subtotal	510,000	820,000	120,000	20,000	20,000	1,490,000

Strategic objective 3: PGRFA research and development						
Upgrading of PGRFA research facilities	120,000	120,000	0	0	0	240,000
Training and research in plant systematics, seed technology and food processing of PGRFA	500,000	500,000	500,000	500,000	500,000	2,500,000
Training and research in novel techniques including marker assisted breeding and gene mapping	500,000	500,000	500,000	500,000	500,000	2,500,000
Development of short courses on PGRFA	50,000	0	0	0	0	50,000
Inclusion of PGRFA courses in undergraduate studies	20,000	0	0	0	0	20,000
Subtotal	1,190,000	1,120,000	1,000,000	1,000,000	1,000,000	5,310,000

Strategic objective 4: Capacity development						
Enhance the capacity and role of local community participation in management of PGRFA	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	250,000
Increase technical capacities of farmers to develop, improve, document and maintain farmer varieties	200,000	200,000	200,000	200,000	200,000	1,000,000
strengthen the capacity of technical staff in PGRFA development and management	150,000	150,000	150,000	150,000	150,000	750,000
Enhance the capacity of decision makers for better understanding and appreciation of PGRFA issues	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	250,000
Upgrading of conservation facilities (gene banks, community seed banks, seed processing equipment, greenhouses, Irrigation facilities)	500,000	500,000	500,000	500,000	500,000	2,500,000
Subtotal	950,000	950,000	950,000	950,000	950,000	4,750,000

Strategic objective 5: Knowledge management and information dissemination						
Information gathering, documentation and dissemination	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	250,000
Development of communication strategy	50,000	0	0	0	0	50,000
PGRFA dissemination conferences and workshops	120,000	120,000	120,000	120,000	120,000	600,000
Subtotal	220,000	170,000	170,000	170,000	170,000	900,000
Coordination and collaboration						
Steering committee establishment and operation	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	250,000
Resource mobilization	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	50,000	250,000
Subtotal	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	500,000
Monitoring and Evaluation						
Development of monitoring framework and tools	50,000	0	0	0	0	50,000
Baseline study	250,000	0	0	0	0	250,000
Mid-term review	0	0	100,000	0	0	100,000
End line survey	0	0	0	0	250,000	250,000
Routine monitoring	200,000	200,000	200,000	200,000	200,000	1,000,000

Subtotal	500,000	200,000	300,000	200,000	450,000	1,650,000
Capital costs						
Vehicles and motorbikes	1,200,000	0	0	1,200,000	0	2,400,000
Laboratory equipment	300,000	0	300,000	0	0	600,000
Computers and accessories	75,000	0	75,000	0	75,000	225,000
Subtotal	1,575,000		375,000	1,200,000	75,000	3,225,000
Personnel and administration						
Staff costs	40,000	40,000	40,000	40,000	40,000	200,000
Office running costs	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	100,000	500,000
Subtotal	140,000	140,000	140,000	140,000	140,000	700,000
Grand Total (ZMW)	5,440,000	3,770,000	3,380,000	4,005,000	3,130,000	19,725,000

Annex 1: Institutions and organizations participating in the implementation of the National Strategy for PGRFA and their specific roles

S/N	Institution	Main roles
1	Zambia Agriculture Research Institute	Research and development, conservation and maintenance of PGRFA. seed regeneration multiplication of seed samples, characterization of conserved germplasm and facilitating access to PGRFA.
2	Seed Control and Certification Institute	Variety certification and facilitating release, provide quality control (seed inspections, seed testing in the lab, variety description, variety protection, DNA finger printing).
3	Golden Valley Agricultural Research Trust	Technology development, incubation and dissemination
4	University of Zambia, Mulungushi University, Copperbelt University	Education and research, capacity building, integration of PGRFA in undergraduate and postgraduate curriculum.
5	Community Technology Development Trust	Promoting on-farm conservation and development of PGRFA, through involvement of farmers and farming communities.
7	SADC Plant Genetic Resources Centre	Regional coordination of germplasm conservation and maintenance of base collection to facilitate safety duplication
8	ZASTA	Facilitating involvement and participation of seed companies
9	Zambia National Farmers Union	Involvement of farmers and safeguarding their interests in conservation and use of PGRFA
10	Ministry of Finance	Budgetary support to PGRFA program, mobilization of financial resources
11	Department of Agriculture (Extension services)	Technology dissemination, farmer mobilization, farmer training, providing feedback to different stakeholders

12	Training institutions (NRDC, ZCA, etc.)	Provide training in agriculture, integration of PGRFA in the educational curriculum
13	Civil society and NGOS	Farmer training workshops and awareness, farmer mobilization, demonstration plots, seed fairs, field days.
14	Department of Policy and Planning, Ministry of Agriculture	Domestication of international instruments on PGRFA, integration of PGRFA issues in food and nutrition policies.
15	Ministry of Justice	Development of legislation, including regulations to support the management of PGRFA
16	National Agricultural Information Services	Information dissemination in diverse media outlets, production of documentaries, dissemination of information in local language, covering and reporting on PGRFA activities, information packaging
17	ZEMA	Safeguarding environment for enhancement of PGRFA conservation
19	Department of Natural Resources Ministry of Lands, Natural Resources and Environmental Protection	Environmental and natural resources conservation (in situ conservation of PGRFA)
20	Department of National Parks and Wildlife	Protection and conservation of Zambia's wildlife including crop wild relatives in National Parks and Game Management Areas
21	Department of Forestry	Spearhead sustainable management of the forest resources across the country, including conservation of CWRs through forestry reserves.
22	National Biosafety Authority	Regulation of research and development of genetically modified organisms to ensure safety for human and animal health and the environment

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